

Effect of processing temperature on the bitumen/MDI-PEG reactivity. Fuel Processing Technology 90(4): 525-530

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Abstract

Reactive polymers are lately gaining acceptance to give added value to a residue of the crude oil refining process such as bitumen. The resulting material should display enhanced mechanical properties to be considered for advanced applications in construction. In the present paper, we report the effect of processing temperature on the reaction between bitumen compounds and an isocyanate-based reactive polymer, synthesized by reaction of polymeric MDI (4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate) with a low molecular weight polyethylene-glycol (PEG).

Rheokinetics experiments, viscosity measurements at 60 °C, atomic force microscopy (AFM) characterization, thin layer chromatography (TLC-FID) analysis and thermogravimetric studies (TGA) were performed on the reactive polymer and on samples of MDI-PEG modified bitumen containing 2wt.% of the polymer. Results showed the existence of an optimum processing temperature arisen as a consequence of opposite effects: microstructural availability for the formation of a polymer-bitumen network, reaction ability and polymer thermal degradation.

Consequently, this study aims to serve as a guideline for the refining and asphalt industries facing the stage of selecting the optimum processing parameters.

Keywords: Modified bitumen; MDI-PEG; Rheology; Product engineering.

F1. Evolution of M/M_0 (normalised torque) with time during the preparation of 2 wt. % MDI-PEG modified bitumens at different temperatures between 60 and 180°C, from bitumen with 2 different penetration grades.

F2. AFM pictures corresponding to non-modified bitumens with 2 different penetration grades (A: 150/200, B: 60/70), at 3 selected temperatures (1: 30 °C, 2: 50 °C, 3: 75 °C). Window size: 50 μm ~50 μm .

F3. Flow curves at 60 °C for uncured samples of 2 wt.% MDI-PEG modified bitumen at temperatures between 60 and 180 °C and their corresponding blanks.

F4. Weight loss at 10 °C min⁻¹ between 40 and 600 °C, for PEG, polymeric MDI and MDI-PEG, under air atmosphere.

F5. Isothermal weight loss at 120, 150 and 180 °C for MDI-PEG, and at 180 °C for PEG and polymeric MDI, under air atmosphere.

F6. Flow curves at 60 °C for 50 days cured samples of 2 wt.% MDI-PEG modified bitumen at temperatures between 60 and 180 °C and their corresponding blanks.

F7. AFM pictures at 50 °C corresponding to 150/200 non-modified bitumen (A), and a sample of the same base bitumen modified at 120 °C with 2 wt.% MDI-PEG and cured for 50 days (B). Window size: 30 μm ~30 μm .

F8. Evolution of modification index (defined in Eq. (1)) with processing temperature as a function of curing time, for 2 wt.% MDI-PEG modified bitumens.